

1 **Tailoring composition and nanostructures in supramolecular solvents: Impact on**
2 **the extraction efficiency of polyphenols from vegetal biomass**

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18 **Abstract**

19 Polyphenols are one of the most appreciated antioxidants nowadays. Industry has an
20 enormous interest in their efficient extraction from vegetal biomass, but most of current
21 methods are neither eco-friendly nor cost-effective. Supramolecular solvents (SUPRAS),
22 made up of self-assembled amphiphilic aggregates, have shown a great potential for the
23 extraction of bioactives from biomass as well as for the compliance with many green
24 chemistry criteria. Comparative studies on the extraction capability of different types of
25 SUPRAS are essential for their application-oriented tailoring. In this study, seven
26 SUPRAS made up of reverse hexagonal aggregates and sponge-like structures were
27 synthesized in a variety of hydro-organic mixtures from 1-octanol and 1,2-octanediol,
28 respectively, and their capability for the extraction of polyphenols from raspberries was
29 evaluated. SUPRAS were characterized in terms of formation phase diagrams,
30 composition and structure. Sponge-like SUPRAS of 1,2-octanediol, which had abundant
31 aqueous interconnected channels (35.5-39% w/w), showed excellent solubilisation
32 properties for both the highly polar polyphenol glycoside conjugates and the less polar
33 polyphenols. Optimal values were obtained with SUPRAS of 1,2-octanediol and 1,3-
34 propanediol that provided a total polyphenolic content of 9.57 ± 0.19 mg GAE/g FW
35 sample. This value was up to three times higher than that obtained with ethanolic extracts.
36 Polyphenol glycosides (from quercetin, naringenin, kaempferol, coumaric acid and
37 catechin) were the predominant identified metabolites.

38

39 **Keywords**

40 Supramolecular solvent; Sponge phase; Liquid chromatography-high resolution mass
41 spectrometry; Polyphenol extraction, raspberries.

42

43 **1. Introduction**

44 Polyphenols are secondary plant metabolites with antioxidant properties. They are
45 structurally characterised by the presence of one or various six-carbon aromatic rings and
46 two or more phenolic groups. Antioxidants provide beneficial effects to the human health:
47 they help to avoid heart and neurodegenerative diseases and have positive effects on the
48 immune system [1–3].

49 Thanks to these beneficial properties, polyphenols are interesting for the food, cosmetic
50 and nutraceutical industry [4]. This has led to an increasing interest in the development
51 of cost-effective and greener extraction techniques for these compounds. Polyphenols are
52 present in thousands of plants which contain different profiles of phenolic constituents.
53 Consequently, these techniques should ideally behave as matrix-independent and they
54 should be able to cover a wide polarity range of phenolic compounds. Products, such as
55 cocoa, tea, citrus or berries contain a remarkable concentration of polyphenols [5].
56 Currently, there are not extraction methods that cover the efficient extraction of a wide
57 polarity range of phenolic compounds in different vegetable matrices.

58 The most used extraction methods for polyphenols are still based on conventional
59 extraction with organic solvents. Traditional methods such as heat reflux extraction or
60 Soxhlet extraction use high volumes of organic solvents like methanol, ethanol or iso1-
61 propanol, in a ratio up to 1:100 w/v. These techniques also require long times for
62 extraction, which hinders high sample throughput and increases costs [6,7]. Other authors
63 have proposed the use of hydro-organic or organic solvent mixtures to cover the
64 extraction of a wider range of polyphenols [8]. The consumption of organic solvents has
65 been reduced by the application of auxiliary energies (microwaves, ultrasounds, high
66 temperature, pressure, etc.) or they have been replaced with greener solvents [ionic liquids
67 (IL), deep eutectic solvents (DES), biosolvents, and supercritical fluids] [9–15].
68 Nevertheless, the use of auxiliary energies or of supercritical conditions is costly for
69 process scale-up. IL are also expensive to produce and their constituents are not always
70 eco-friendly. In this sense, the use of DES is a better option. However, in order to achieve
71 efficient extraction of phenolic compounds with these viscous liquids, the application of
72 ultrasound or microwave-assisted energy is usually required, together with relatively high
73 temperatures (40-80 °C), dilution with water to reduce viscosity (5-30% w/w) and long
74 extraction times (up to 90 min) [16–18]. Dispersive liquid-liquid microextraction with

75 DES has been also proposed for the extraction of polyphenols and phytosterols from oils
76 and milk, respectively. These methods, which were oriented to analytical purposes,
77 required multiple sample preparation steps including an initial liquid-liquid extraction
78 step. [19,20]

79 Supramolecular solvents (SUPRAS) are nanostructured liquids generated from colloidal
80 solutions of amphiphiles through spontaneous phenomena of self-assembly and
81 coacervation [21]. Their application to the extraction of bioactive compounds from
82 vegetal biomass has been quite testimonial in the last decade [22-27]. However, because
83 of their unique properties for solute solubilisation, their potential in this field is
84 recognized as highly promising [28,29]. Those particular characteristics of SUPRAS that
85 are of interest for the extraction of bioactive compounds include [28-30]; (i) the presence
86 of *regions of different polarity* in their nanostructures, where a wide polarity range of
87 substances can be efficiently solubilized through mixed mode mechanisms. (ii) The *high*
88 *concentration of amphiphiles* in the SUPRAS (~0.1-1 g/mL) that results in a large number
89 of binding sites. (iii) The *discontinuous character* of SUPRAS, formed by coacervate
90 droplets, that provide a large surface area and, consequently, fast mass transfer. (iv) The
91 possibility of *tailoring SUPRAS* nanostructures, composition and properties by judicious
92 selection of amphiphiles and the environment for coacervation. (v) The compliance of
93 SUPRAS with many of the criteria set for *green solvents* (e.g. high performance for the
94 intended purpose, synthesis carried out through an energy-saving process that has a high-
95 atom economy, etc.) [33].

96 So far, the most used amphiphiles for extracting bioactive compounds have been non-
97 ionic surfactants (e.g. surfactants from the Triton X series, alcohols and carboxylic acids).
98 SUPRAS formation was induced by the increase of the temperature of the aqueous
99 colloidal solution [23-26] or by the addition of water (a poor solvent for the amphiphile)
100 to the organic colloidal solution [22,27-29]. In both cases, the coacervation-inducing
101 agent (temperature or water) promoted the growth of the amphiphilic aggregates present
102 in the colloidal solutions by reducing the repulsions among their amphiphile head groups
103 or by decreasing the solvent molecules available for head-group solvation. The extraction
104 efficiency of bioactive compounds (e.g. betaine, saponins, anthraquinones, phenolic
105 compounds, caffeine, carotenoids, etc.) surpassed that of conventional organic solvents.
106 Thus, Ribeiro et al.[23] found that SUPRAS were superior for extraction of saponins from
107 sisal waste (recovery 98.4%) compared with an ethanolic solution (recovery 38.6%). Also

108 Torres-Valenzuela et al [27] found that SUPRAS extracted ~12-fold and ~19-fold more
109 caffeine than methanol and ethanol, respectively, from coffee cherry pulp.

110 Both the constituents and the nanostructure of SUPRAS are expected to greatly influence
111 the quantity and the profile of the extracted bioactive compounds. On this basis, this study
112 aims to get an insight and to gain knowledge into those SUPRAS properties driving the
113 extraction of compounds with different polarity, and to lay the foundations to design
114 tailor-made SUPRAS to target specific classes of compounds. For this purpose, seven
115 SUPRAS made up of reverse hexagonal aggregates and sponge-like structures were
116 synthesized in different hydro-organic mixtures from 1-octanol and 1,2-octanediol,
117 respectively, and their capability for the extraction of polyphenols from raspberries was
118 evaluated. The hydro-organic mixtures were made from protic (ethanol, 1-propanol, 1,3-
119 propanediol) and aprotic (tetrahydrofuran) solvents. SUPRAS were characterized in
120 terms of phase diagrams, composition and structure. Extraction efficiencies for the
121 different SUPRAS were evaluated in terms of total polyphenol content and profile.
122 Below, results are discussed on the basis of SUPRAS composition and structure.

123

124 **2. Experimental**

125 *2.1 Reagents*

126 All chemicals were of analytical-reagent grade and employed as supplied.
127 Tetrahydrofuran (THF), ethanol, 1-octanol and acetic acid were purchase from Panreac
128 (Barcelona, Spain). 1-Propanol, gallic acid and Folin-Ciocalteu reagent were supplied
129 by Sigma-Aldrich (Steinheim, Germany) and methanol by Riedel-de Haën (Seelze,
130 Germany). 1,2-octanediol and sodium carbonate were purchase from Aldrich (St Louis,
131 USA) and 1,3-propanediol was supplied by Acros Organics (Geel, Belgium). Ultra-pure
132 water was produced in an Elix® Essential 3 water purification system by Merck Millipore
133 (Madrid, Spain).

134 *2.2 Apparatus*

135 SUPRAS preparation was performed using a vortex for mixing ingredients and a
136 centrifuge for accelerating phase separation. The following devices were used: Vortex
137 mixer equipped with an attachment for different size tubes from Heathrow Scientific

138 (Vernon Hills, USA), a Mixtasel BLT digitally regulated centrifuge equipped with an
139 angle rotor 16×15 mL from JP Selecta (Barcelona, Spain), a Reax Top vortex mixer
140 equipped with an attachment for centrifuge microtubes from Heidolph (Schwabach,
141 Germany) and a MINICEN centrifuge from Ortoalresa (Madrid, Spain).

142 A Coulometric Karl Fischer titrator with generator electrode without diaphragm from
143 Metrohm (Herisau, Switzerland) and a digital calliper from Medid Precision, S.A.
144 (Barcelona, Spain) were used to measure the water content and volume of the SUPRAS,
145 respectively. The analysis of residual amphiphile in the equilibrium solution after
146 SUPRAS preparation as well as the identification of the phenolic compounds in SUPRAS
147 extracts were done with a Bruker ELUTE UHPLC coupled to a hybrid ion mobility triple
148 quadrupole/TOF (TimsTOF, Q-TOF) equipped with an ESI source operating in positive
149 and negative modes from Bruker Daltonics (Bremen, Germany). The measurement of the
150 total polyphenolic content in SUPRAS extracts was done using a Thermo Spectronic
151 Helios ϵ spectrophotometer from Labbox (Madrid, Spain).

152 The characterization of SUPRAS structure was carried out with an EVO LS 15 scanning
153 electron microscope from Zeiss (Oberkochen, Germany)

154 *2.3 Phase diagrams*

155 Phase diagrams for the ternary mixtures of 1-octanol:water:organic solvent and 1,2-
156 octanediol:water:organic solvent were constructed in order to delineate the region for
157 SUPRAS formation. Mixtures of 10 mL of 1-octanol or of 1,2-octanediol (up to 15% w/v)
158 were prepared in hydro-organic solutions (from 95:5 v/v to 20:80 v/v water:organic
159 solvent). Organic solvents were ethanol, 1-propanol, 1,3-propanediol and
160 tetrahydrofuran. The mixtures were vortex-shaken for 5 min to favour the contact between
161 their components and then centrifuged (2,500 rpm, 5 min) to accelerate phase separation.
162 The criterion used to determine the formation of SUPRAS was the formation of two
163 immiscible isotropic liquid phases in the system. The SUPRAS phase stand at the top and
164 the equilibrium solution at the bottom (containing a residual amount of amphiphile near
165 the critical aggregation concentration, water and organic solvent).

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168 *2.4 SUPRAS volume and composition*

169 The generated volume of SUPRAS under different synthesis conditions was calculated
170 by measuring its height in a cylindrical tube with a digital calliper and using the equation
171 $V=\pi\cdot r^2\cdot h$.

172 The water content in SUPRAS was determined with a coulometric Karl Fischer (KF)
173 titrator. For this purpose, aliquots of 50 μ L SUPRAS were weighed and dissolved in 1-2
174 mL of MeOH. Aliquots of 200 μ L of the resulting solutions were injected into the KF
175 titrator. The concentration of amphiphile in SUPRAS was determined gravimetrically
176 after the evaporation of water and the organic solvent. For this purpose, 200 μ L aliquots
177 of SUPRAS were weighed, added to an Eppendorf tube and left to evaporate at room
178 temperature for 48 h. The water content of the residue was measured by KF titration to
179 ensure that all the water was evaporated. Finally, the concentration of organic solvent in
180 SUPRAS was calculated by weight difference.

181 After SUPRAS formation, the residual concentration of amphiphile remaining in the
182 bottom equilibrium solution was measured by LC-APCI (atmospheric pressure chemical
183 ionization) (+)-(high resolution)-MS to monitor acetonitrile adducts of 1-octanol and 1,2-
184 octanediol (see table **S1**) [31]. Haga clic o pulse aquí para escribir texto. Chromatographic
185 separation was carried out on a RESTEK C₁₈ column (100 mm x 3.0 mm, 3 μ m) preceded
186 by a Phenomenex KJ 0-4282 Security Guard Cartridge Kit precolumn. The mobile phase
187 consisted of (A) water and (B) acetonitrile. The gradient elution program consisted in
188 isocratic conditions for 1 min at 60% (v/v) B and then a linear gradient from 60% to 99%
189 (v/v) of B for 9 min followed by isocratic conditions at 99% (v/v) B for 2.5 min (flow
190 rate 0.2 mL/min). Finally, initial conditions were re-equilibrated for 7 min. The column
191 temperature was set at 35 °C. Source parameters were as follows: dry heater 200 °C, dry
192 gas flow 3 L·min⁻¹; nebulizer gas pressure 2.5 bar; capillary voltage, 2,500V. Acquisition
193 was done at bbCID (broad band collision induced dissociation) mode (3 Hz, focus on,
194 profile spectra).

195 *2.5 SUPRAS structural characterization*

196 The SUPRAS structure was elucidated by scanning electron microscopy (SEM). The
197 sample preparation was as follow: 10 μ L of SUPRAS were fixed with glutaraldehyde and
198 embedded with a 6% (w/v) agarose aqueous solution. The sample was washed three times

199 with sodium cacodylate and stained with OsO₄ (1%, w/v) for contrast enhancement.
200 Samples were then dehydrated with a graded series of acetone (30, 50, 70, 80, 90, 100 %,
201 v/v) and dried using the critical point drying. Finally, samples were coated with gold and
202 observed under SEM. The accelerating voltage was set at 10 kV.

203 2.6 SUPRAS extraction of polyphenols in raspberries

204 The extraction capacity of the different SUPRAS was investigated by extracting
205 polyphenolic metabolites from raspberries (*Rubus idaeus*) that were bought at a local
206 supermarket in Córdoba (Spain) and blended until homogenized. SUPRAS of 1-octanol
207 and 1,2-octanediol were prepared by dissolving 15% w/v of amphiphile in a 15:85 % v/v
208 mixture of organic solvent (ethanol, 1-propanol, 1,3-propanediol or THF) and water (total
209 volume of the synthesis solution 50 mL). Both the SUPRAS and the corresponding
210 equilibrium solutions were separately stored at 4 °C in closed polypropylene bottles until
211 use for at least 1 month.

212 Aliquots of 200 mg of sample (wet weight) were mixed with 400 µL of SUPRAS and 400
213 µL of equilibrium solution. The mixture was vortex-shaken (15 min) to favour the
214 extraction and centrifuged (15,000 rpm, 15 min) to accelerate the separation of the
215 SUPRAS phase. SUPRAS extracts were directly analysed with LC-ESI(-/+)-(high
216 resolution)MS/MS for the identification of the main phenolic compounds and by UV
217 spectrophotometry for the determination of the total polyphenolic content by the Folin-
218 Ciocalteu method.

219 For LC-(ESI)-MS/MS analysis, the stationary phase was the same as that described in
220 section 2.4. The mobile phase consisted of (A) water and (B) methanol both containing 5
221 mM ammonium formate and 0.01% v/v formic acid for ESI positive mode and 5 mM
222 ammonium acetate for ESI negative mode. The gradient elution program was the same in
223 both polarity modes and consisted in a linear gradient from 4% to 99% v/v of B for 16
224 min (flow rate 0.2 mL/min) and then isocratic conditions with 99% v/v of B for 3 min
225 (flow rate 0.48 mL/min). Finally, initial conditions were re-equilibrated for 7 min. The
226 column temperature was set at 40 °C. Source parameters were as follows: dry heater 200
227 °C, dry gas flow 3 L·min⁻¹; nebulizer gas pressure 2.5 bar; capillary voltage, 3,500V.
228 Acquisition was done with *autoMSMS* mode (10 Hz, focus on, profile spectra). The
229 identification of the metabolites was performed using a library of plant metabolites
230 administered by the equipment vendor and the program MetaboScape (Bruker).

231 Identification criteria were based on exact mass (≤ 5 ppm) and isotopic pattern fit (mSigma
232 ≤ 200).

233 For the quantification of total polyphenolic content, SUPRAS extracts were diluted 1:30
234 v/v with MeOH. After that, 50 μL of the diluted sample, 1.5 mL of distilled water, 100
235 μL of 0.1N Folin Ciocalteu reagent and 300 μL of a 7,5 % w/v sodium carbonate solution
236 were added to 2 mL Eppendorf tubes. After 90 minutes in darkness, the absorbance was
237 measured at 760 nm. Quantitative analysis was conducted using standard solutions of
238 gallic acid, prepared in ultrapure water in the concentration range of 5–1000 mg/L, and
239 subjected to the same procedure than samples.

240 **3. Results and discussion**

241 An array of SUPRAS were synthesized from two amphiphiles (1-octanol and 1,2-
242 octanediol) dissolved in protic (ethanol, 1-propanol, 1,3-propanediol) and aprotic (THF)
243 solvents by addition of water as the coacervation-inducing agent. Water, a poor solvent
244 for these amphiphiles, promoted amphiphile-amphiphile over amphiphile-solvent
245 interactions, which led to aggregate growth and liquid-phase separation [30]. By the
246 synthesis and characterization of these SUPRAS, we aimed to investigate the influence
247 of the polar group of the amphiphile and the coacervation medium on both SUPRAS
248 composition and nanostructure, and how these factors influenced their capability for
249 extraction of polyphenols in plants. This class of bioactive compounds include a wide
250 variety of structures and physicochemical properties, so they were considered excellent
251 candidates for the purpose of this study.

252 *3.1 SUPRAS synthesis*

253 **Figures 1** and **2** show the range of concentrations of amphiphile and organic solvent
254 where SUPRAS from 1-octanol and 1,2-octanediol were formed respectively, for each
255 of the ternary mixtures. Above the SUPRAS region, the percentage of water in the ternary
256 mixture was too low to induce the coacervation and below it, the percentage of organic
257 solvent was not enough for amphiphile solubilisation. 1-Octanol did not generate
258 SUPRAS in 1,3-propanediol:water mixtures.

259 The phase diagrams of 1-octanol were wider and SUPRAS were formed at much lower
260 percentages of water (30-40% v/v) than those from 1,2-octanediol (70-80% v/v). The
261 reason is that adding a second OH- group at the polar head of the amphiphile remarkably

262 increases its polarity. Water solubility of 1-octanol is 540 mg/L at 25 °C while for 1,2-
263 octanediol it is 3 g/L at 20°C (experimental data obtained from PubChem database). Due
264 to the lower water solubility of 1-octanol in comparison with 1,2-octanediol, it was
265 expected that a lower concentration of coacervation-inducing agent would be required to
266 induce its self-assembly.

267

268

269 **Figure 1.** Phase diagrams of 1-octanol in mixtures of water and organic solvents
270 [tetrahydrofuran (THF) (A), 1-propanol (B) and ethanol (C)].

271 Clear differences were observed between SUPRAS of 1-octanol formed in different
272 organic solvents (Fig. 1). Thus, the solvents with the lowest dielectric constants gave the
273 broadest regions for SUPRAS formation, as it occurred for THF ($\epsilon=7.4$ at 25 °C),

274 followed by 1-propanol ($\epsilon=20.33$ at 25 °C) and ethanol ($\epsilon=25.3$ at 25 °C). However, this
275 behaviour was different for the more polar 1,2-octanediol-SUPRAS, for which the
276 different solvents generated similar phase diagrams (Fig. 2).

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280 **Figure 2.** Phase diagrams of 1,2-octanediol in mixtures of water and organic solvents
281 [tetrahydrofuran (THF) (A), 1-propanol (B), ethanol (C) and 1,3-propanediol (D)].

282

283 In order to determine the efficiency of the SUPRAS synthesis, the concentration of
284 amphiphile remaining in the equilibrium solution after SUPRAS formation was measured
285 by LC-(APCI)-MS (section 2.4). Average values for 1-octanol-based SUPRAS were in
286 the range 1.3-3.1 g/L, 0.08-1.96 g/L and 0.28-0.43 g/L when using THF, 1-propanol or
287 ethanol, respectively. For 1,2-octanediol-based SUPRAS, the concentration of
288 amphiphile in the equilibrium solution was a bit higher, which is in agreement with its
289 higher water solubility and it was in the ranges 8.3-8.6 g/L, 4.9-6.6 g/L, 8.6-8.7 g/L and
290 10.2-17.2 g/L when using THF, 1-propanol, ethanol or 1,3-propanediol, respectively.
291 Accordingly, the percentage of amphiphile incorporated into the SUPRAS phase after the
292 synthesis was ~90-100 % for both 1-octanol and 1,2-octanediol-SUPRAS under the
293 studied experimental conditions (**Table S2**). Thus, the synthesis of 1-octanol- and 1,2-
294 octanediol-based SUPRAS at room temperature is a high atom-economy process [33],
295 which is a requirement for the preparation of green solvents.

296 *3.2 SUPRAS volume*

297 The volume of SUPRAS generated by coacervation was investigated as a function of the
298 relative proportion of the synthesis ingredients. **Figures S1** and **S2** show the volume of
299 SUPRAS, expressed as μL of SUPRAS per mL of synthesis solution, as a function of the
300 percentage of amphiphile and of organic solvent. As displayed in **Tables S3** and **S4**, it
301 was found that, in all cases, the volume of SUPRAS increased linearly with the percentage
302 of the amphiphile (at a fixed concentration of organic solvent) and exponentially with the
303 organic solvent (at a fixed concentration of the amphiphile). This means that all SUPRAS
304 behaved as environmental-responsive materials since their volume changed with the
305 environment for coacervation (i.e. the organic solvent/water ratio). These trends are in
306 agreement with previously reported SUPRAS [34,35].

307 Non-linear regression was used to fit a model and propose general equations to predict
308 the volume of SUPRAS as a function of the percentage of amphiphile and organic solvent
309 in the synthesis mixture. **Table 1** shows the predicted equations. The goodness of the fit
310 of these equations are shown in SI (**Figure S3**).

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312

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Table 1. Equations to predict the generated volume of SUPRAS as a function of the percentage of amphiphile (% w/v) and of organic solvent (% v/v) in the synthesis solution

SUPRAS		Volume equation	R ²
Amphiphile	Organic solvent		
1-Octanol	THF	$y = [(0.207x + 13.176) \cdot z] + (6.537x - 96.319)$	0.9532
1-Octanol	Ethanol	$y = [(0.502x + 6.089) \cdot z] + (-1.554x + 29.703)$	0.9347
1-Octanol	1-Propanol	$y = [(0.117x + 4.265) \cdot z] + (12.893x - 85.864)$	0.8922
1,2-Octanediol	THF	$y = [(0.453x + 16.460) \cdot z] + (2.199x - 30.981)$	0.9893
1,2-Octanediol	Ethanol	$y = [(0.520x + 14.296) \cdot z] + (-0.982x - 1.531)$	0.9932
1,2-Octanediol	1-Propanol	$y = [(0.587x + 15.944) \cdot z] + (3.276x - 35.388)$	0.9813
1,2-Octanediol	1,3-Propanediol	$y = [(0.431x + 11.182) \cdot z] + (-2.190x + 25.844)$	0.9985

y: SUPRAS volume ($\mu\text{L}/\text{mL}$ mixture); x: % v/v organic solvent; z: % w/v amphiphile

315

316 Under identical synthesis conditions, the volume of SUPRAS from 1,2-octanediol was
 317 around 1.4-fold higher than that obtained from 1-octanol, independently of the hydro-
 318 organic mixture. This behaviour can be easily inferred from the comparison of the
 319 equation coefficients in Tables S3 and S4. The use of different organic solvents for the
 320 synthesis of SUPRAS with the same amphiphile did not result in large differences in
 321 SUPRAS volumes.

322 3.3 SUPRAS chemical composition

323 **Tables 2 and 3** show the SUPRAS composition at 15% w/v of amphiphile and different
 324 organic solvent:water ratios in the synthesis solution. Regarding 1-octanol-based
 325 SUPRAS (Table 2), as the percentage of water (coacervating agent) in the bulk solution
 326 decreased, the water and organic solvent contents in SUPRAS increased, and
 327 consequently, the amphiphile percentage decreased. Since the volume of SUPRAS also
 328 increased accordingly, the amphiphile just become more diluted and solvated in this
 329 phase. This behaviour indicated that the chemical composition of the 1-octanol-based
 330 SUPRAS was environment responsive and that it could be tailored by just changing the
 331 organic solvent:water ratio in the synthesis solution. This is also in agreement with the
 332 fact that higher concentration of coacervating agent (water) give rise to more dehydrated
 333 polar head groups and, consequently, to more packed SUPRAS phases with less water
 334 content, as it happens in salt-induced or temperature-induced SUPRAS [32,35].

335 The percentage of solvent incorporated into the SUPRAS phase was directly related to its
336 dielectric constant, so that the higher the solvency power of the organic solvent for the
337 nonpolar part of the amphiphile (lower ϵ), the higher the incorporated value. For example,
338 values of 16.8 ± 0.3 , 8.7 ± 0.8 and $3.9\pm 0.5\%$ w/w of organic solvent were measured in 1-
339 octanol-based SUPRAS produced with 10% v/v of THF, 1-propanol and ethanol,
340 respectively. Contrarily, the maximum percentage of water incorporated in 1-octanol-
341 based SUPRAS was inversely related to the dielectric constant of the solvent, so that
342 values of 14.3 ± 0.5 , 24.4 ± 0 and $32.9\pm 0.3\%$ w/w of water were obtained for SUPRAS
343 prepared in THF, 1-propanol and ethanol, respectively.

344 Comparing the composition of 1-octanol (Table 2) and 1,2-octanediol-based SUPRAS
345 (Table 3), the most significant difference was the higher water content of the latter. 1,2-
346 octanediol-SUPRAS contained percentages of water around 35.9 ± 0.9 , 38 ± 1 , 36.6 ± 0.9
347 and $38.4\pm 0.8\%$ w/w using THF, 1-propanol, ethanol and 1,3-propanediol, respectively;
348 being this value quite independent of the solubility properties of the organic solvent. The
349 same behaviour was previously reported for 1,2-decanediol-based SUPRAS for which
350 values of water around 30% w/w were measured [34]. The higher water content of diols
351 in comparison with simple alcohols is due to the double head of the amphiphile leading
352 to a higher hydration degree. Furthermore, amphiphilic aggregates made up of double-
353 headed surfactants are expected to be more open. Micellar sizes and aggregation numbers
354 decrease as the number of head groups increase due to electrostatic repulsion and/or steric
355 hindrance, thus favoring the interactions with water molecules [36].

356 As it occurred for 1-octanol-based SUPRAS, the percentage of amphiphile increased with
357 the increase of the coacervating agent in the bulk solution leading to more packed phases
358 (Table 3). However, differently from 1-octanol-based SUPRAS, the ones synthesized
359 from 1,2-octanediol were less solvated in terms of organic solvent content, which is
360 probably solvating the amphiphile hydrocarbon chains, while the content of the water
361 remained almost constant. Taking into account that the amphiphile and the organic
362 solvent concentration in 1,2-octanediol-based SUPRAS vary with the composition of the
363 bulk solution, we can conclude that they are environmental responsive materials too.

364

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Table 2. 1-Octanol-based SUPRAS composition (at 15% w/v amphiphile)

Synthesis conditions	SUPRAS composition (% w/w)			
	THF:H ₂ O (%v/v)	1-Octanol	H ₂ O	THF
5:95		84.4±0.2	3.7±0.1	11.9±0.4
10:90		78.7±0.3	4.52±0.04	16.8±0.3
15:85		68.8±0.7	5.1±0.2	26±0.9
20:80		61.4±0.2	6.00±0.06	32.6±0.3
30:70		47±2	6.9±0.1	46±2
40:60		39.4±0.5	8.6±0.2	52.0±0.3
50:50		31.4±0.8	9.8±0.7	58.8±0.1
60:40		26.2±0.1	11.8±0.3	62±0.4
70:30		21.3±0.8	14.3±0.5	64.4±1.2
1-Propanol:H₂O (%v/v)		1-Octanol	H ₂ O	Propanol
5:95		90.3±0.2	6,338±0,002	3.4±0.2
10:90		84±0.7	7.3±0.1	8.7±0.8
15:85		76.1±0.2	9.05±0.03	14.8±0.3
20:80		76±11	9.9±0.4	13.9±0.9
30:70		53.9±0.6	13.7±0.3	32.4±0.3
40:60		41.7±0.4	18.94±0.04	39.3±0.4
50:50		34.4±0.9	24.6±0.3	41±0.6
Ethanol:H₂O (%v/v)		1-Octanol	H ₂ O	Ethanol
5:95		93.9±0.5	4.51±0.06	1.6±0.5
10:90		91.2±0.5	4.93±0.02	3.9±0.5
15:85		88.4±0.6	5.7±0.2	5.9±0.4
20:80		84.1±0.1	6.6±0.2	9.2±0.1
30:70		72.8±0.1	9.37±0.03	17.8±0.1
40:60		57.7±0.7	15.7±0.3	27±1
50:50		41.2±0.6	32.9±0.3	25.9±0.9

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Table 3. 1,2-octanediol-SUPRAS composition (at 15% w/v amphiphile)

Synthesis conditions	SUPRAS composition (% w/w)		
	1,2-octanediol	H ₂ O	THF
THF:H₂O (% ,v/v)			
5:95	52.4±0.4	35.4±0.7	12±1
10:90	44±3	36±1	20±4
15:85	38±1	36.4±0.7	25.3±0.7
20:80	32±2	38.6±0.3	29±2
1-Propanol:H₂O (% , v/v)	1,2-octanediol	H ₂ O	Propanol
5:95	58±2	37.7±0.2	4±2
10:90	50.8±0.1	36±2	13±2
15:85	43.1±0.1	39±1	18±2
20:80	34.1±0.1	43.4±1	22.5±0.9
Ethanol:H₂O (% , v/v)	1,2-octanediol	H ₂ O	Ethanol
5:95	53.4±0.3	38±1	9±1
10:90	49.7±0.7	36.4±0.3	13.9±0.4
15:85	52.2±0.2	35.8±0.9	12±1
20:80	48±2	36.8±0.4	15±1
1,3-Propanediol:H₂O (% , v/v)	1,2-octanediol	H ₂ O	Propanediol
15:85	39.6±0.2	37.5±0.2	22.90±0.02
20:80	41.62±3.1	35.5±0.1	23±3
30:70	34.5±0.5	35.0±0.7	30.5±0.2

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375 *3.4 SUPRAS nanostructure*

376 The structure of SUPRAS of alkanols in THF:water media have been reported by
377 Ballesteros-Gómez et al. [35]. These SUPRAS were described as clusters of inverted
378 hexagonal aggregates where the alcohol groups of alkanols surrounded aqueous cavities
379 and the THF solvated their hydrocarbon chains. Figure **S4** shows typical micrographs
380 obtained by optical and cryo-SEM microscopy, along with a schematic of the reported
381 nanostructures. The size of the aqueous cavities can be tailored by controlling the
382 tetrahydrofuran (THF):water ratio in the synthesis mixture. Thus, the lower the water
383 content in the synthesis solution, the larger the aqueous cores in the SUPRAS
384 nanostructures.

385 Inverted hexagonal aggregates were also supposed to be produced in SUPRAS
386 synthesized from 1-octanol in ethanol-water and 1-propanol-water, here firstly
387 investigated, on the basis of the similar variation of their chemical composition as
388 function of the organic solvent:water ratio in the synthesis solution (Table 2). Thus, the
389 percentage of water in the SUPRAS increased as the water content in the synthesis
390 solution decreased, a behaviour that, so far, has been exclusively found in inverted
391 hexagonal aggregates [33].

392 Regarding the SUPRAS made up of 1,2-octanediol, all of them here firstly investigated,
393 González-Rubio et al. recently reported that SUPRAS synthesized from 1,2-decanediol
394 in THF:water media gave sponge phases [32]. The different morphology found for
395 alkanols (i.e. hexagonal phases) and 1,2-decanediol (i.e. sponge phases) is a consequence
396 of the very different packing parameter (g) of both amphiphiles. The packing parameter
397 depends on both the volume and length of the hydrophobic chain and the effective area
398 per head group [37]. An extra -OH group at the polar head of the amphiphile significantly
399 increases the area of the polar head group, so that the packing parameter for 1-octanol is
400 1.032 and for 1,2-octanediol is 0.514. These values are commonly used to predict the
401 morphology of the amphiphilic aggregates near the critical aggregation concentration but,
402 so far, they are not useful in predicting the morphology of SUPRAS phases where the
403 concentration of amphiphile is so high as 20-90% w/w (Tables 2 and 3). Nevertheless,
404 without a doubt, the structure of the amphiphile, and so the packing parameter, is a critical
405 factor in driving the resulting SUPRAS nanostructures

406 The nanostructures of 1,2-octanediol-based SUPRAS were investigated by SEM (section
407 2.5). **Figure 3** shows representative micrographs obtained for SUPRAS prepared with
408 15% w/v amphiphile in (A) ethanol:water and (B) THF:water mixtures at a proportion of
409 15:85 v/v. The same results were obtained for the other hydro-organic mixtures tested
410 (i.e. 1-propanol:water and 1,2-propanediol-water). SEM micrographs showed typical
411 features of a sponge morphology [38,39]; ellipsoidal structures nearly flat and surrounded
412 by a network of curved areas with a smooth appearance (Figure 3A and B). The sponge
413 phase consisted of a random 3D amphiphile bilayer network separated by water pores or
414 interconnected channels (Figure 3C). As mentioned before and under the different
415 synthesis conditions (different organic solvents and organic solvent:water mixtures) the
416 water content of these channels remained constant (average 35.9 ± 0.9 %, w/w). These
417 results are in agreement with those recently reported by our group for SUPRAS of 1,2-

418 decanediol in mixtures of THF:water [34]. Consequently, the difference in two carbon
419 atoms of the hydrophobic tail did not influence the SUPRAS structure.

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421

422 **Figure 3.** SEM micrographs of 1,2 octanediol-based SUPRAS synthesized in (A, C)
423 ethanol:water and (B) THF:water. Synthesis conditions: 15% (w/v) of amphiphile and
424 15:85, v/v organic solvent:water.

425 3.5 Influence of SUPRAS composition and nanostructure on their capability for the
426 extraction of polyphenols from raspberries

427 The seven SUPRAS synthesized with 1-octanol and 1,2-octanediol were applied to the
428 extraction of polyphenols from raspberries (section 2.6) in order to compare their
429 extraction efficiency for these bioactive compounds. Main extraction techniques and
430 organic solvents used for isolation of polyphenols from red fruits, including raspberries,
431 have been discussed by Hidalgo and Almajano [40]. Among the solvents investigated
432 (e.g. water, acetone, hexane, ethyl acetate, ethanol, methanol, etc.), ethanol was the most
433 efficient for extraction of antioxidants from red fruits [40-42].

434 **Figure 4** shows the total polyphenolic content [mg gallic acid equivalents (GAE)/g fresh
435 weight (FW) sample] for each SUPRAS. Pure ethanol was also employed for comparison
436 as an established media for the extraction of polyphenols. According to bibliography [40]
437 the total polyphenolic content in raspberries by different extraction methods was in the
438 range 2.6-3.7 mg GAE/g FW sample, what is in agreement with the total polyphenolic
439 content obtained in our study by employing ethanol (3.42±0.05 mg GAE/g FW sample).

440

441 **Figure 4.** Total polyphenolic content in SUPRAS extracts (15% w/v amphiphile, 15:85
442 v/v organic solvent:water) and in a conventional ethanol extract from raspberries.

443 In general, 1-octanol-based SUPRAS extracted polyphenols less efficiently than
444 SUPRAS of 1,2-octanediol, and only those prepared in THF reached similar extraction
445 rates than that of pure ethanol (4.16 ± 0.18 and 3.42 ± 0.05 mg GAE/g FW sample,
446 respectively). The sponge-like SUPRAS were more efficient extraction phases, being also
447 superior to ethanol. The higher water content of these SUPRAS (35.5-39% w/w for 1,2-
448 octanediol-SUPRAS and 4.5-9.1 % w/w for 1-octanol-SUPRAS under the selected
449 synthesis conditions) and their higher expected surface area and more open structure
450 could be the reasoning for this behaviour.

451 Regarding the influence of the organic solvents in both types of SUPRAS, which were
452 expected to be solvating the hydrocarbon layers of the aggregates, those that were protic
453 were more efficient as their polarity increased (1,3-propanediol>ethanol>1-propanol),
454 while the aprotic THF followed a different trend. Optimal values were obtained with
455 SUPRAS of 1,2-octanediol and 1,3-propanediol that provided a total polyphenolic
456 content of 9.57 ± 0.19 mg GAE/g FW sample. This value was almost three times higher
457 than the one obtained with the ethanol extraction method and than those that were
458 previously reported [40]. These results suggest that the high polarity microenvironments
459 in SUPRAS, along with the strong dispersion interactions provided by the hydrocarbon
460 chains of the amphiphile, give an optimal balance for the efficient solubilisation of
461 polyphenols. It is worth mentioning that the composition of all SUPRAS, except for those
462 with THF, would be readily compatible with cosmetic applications (according to CosIng,
463 *European Commission database for information on cosmetic substances and*
464 *ingredients*).

465 In order to find a consistent explanation to the unlike extraction behaviour obtained for
466 the different types of SUPRAS, the phenolic profile was investigated by LC-high
467 resolution (QTOF) MS/MS analysis. The list of identified phenolic compounds and
468 metabolites, along with the exact mass of MS and MS/MS, is shown in **Table S5**. The
469 chemical structure of these compounds is depicted in **Table 4**. Glycosides of phenolic
470 compounds were the predominant metabolites. Berries are rich in sugars, and therefore,
471 polyphenols can easily form glycosides with the sugars present in the matrix. Adding a
472 sugar to the molecule increase the polarity of the parent compound, so that glycosides are
473 always more polar than the molecule from which they derive. Their octanol-water
474 constant, expressed as log, for the identified phenolic compounds (data for glycosides
475 were not found) was from -0.481 to 1.76.

476

477

478 **Figure 5.** Extraction of quercetin, kaempferol and their glycosides from raspberries employing different SUPRAS.

479 Relative extraction efficiencies (expressed as peak absolute areas) for the most abundant
480 phenolic compounds and/or metabolites in SUPRAS extracts are shown in **Figure 5**. The
481 relative extraction efficiencies for other identified compounds are shown in **Figure S5**.
482 For some phenolics, glycosides were the most abundant bioactives (e.g. quercetin
483 rhamnetinhexoside or kaempferol hexoside, Figure 5) while for other ones the
484 predominant form was the parent compound (e.g. catechin or coumaric acid, Figure S5).

485 By comparison of the relative extraction efficiency of the phenolic compounds and their
486 glycosides, a similar trend was observed in most of cases. As the polarity of the molecule
487 increased due to the addition of increasing sugar units (e.g. quercetin
488 rhamnetinhexoside>quercetin hexoside>quercetin; kaempferol dihexoside> kaempferol
489 hexoside>kaempferol, see Figure 5), the extraction was clearly more efficient by using
490 1,2-octanediol-based SUPRAS than 1-octanol-based SUPRAS. For example, by using
491 1,2-octanediol-based SUPRAS, the extraction was more than 2 times higher for
492 kaempferol and kaempferol-hexoside and it was 9 times higher for the most polar
493 kaempferol-dihexoside. These results were in agreement with the measured total phenolic
494 content. We could conclude that SUPRAS of diols greatly improved the extraction
495 efficiency of medium polar and especially of very polar compounds in comparison with
496 SUPRAS based on simple alcohols. The same trend was observed for catechin hexoside
497 and coumaric acid hexoside in comparison with the parent compounds (Fig. S5).

498 The influence of the different organic solvents for SUPRAS preparation on the extraction
499 efficiency had a less defined pattern for 1,2-octanediol-based SUPRAS compared to 1-
500 octanol-based SUPRAS, in which THF was the most effective solvent. This is probably
501 due to the fact that the water content in SUPRAS is the most influential parameter for the
502 extraction of very polar compounds and this content is independent on the type of organic
503 solvent in diol-based SUPRAS.

504

505 **Table 4.** Chemical structure of the identified phenolic compounds.

Quercetin	Quercetin arabinoside	Quercetin hexoside	Quercetin rhamnetinhexoside	Naringenin hexoside
Kaempferol	Kaempferol hexoside	Kaempferol dihexoside	Coumaric acid	Coumaric acid hexoside
Catechin	Catechin hexoside	Catechin dihexoside	Chlorogenic acid	Procyanidin dimer

506

507 **4. Conclusions**

508 SUPRAS composition and nanostructure can be easily tailored by judicious selection of
509 the amphiphile and the environmental conditions for coacervation. In this study, we prove
510 that this tailoring is essential for the development of application-oriented SUPRAS with
511 high efficacy for the intended purpose. Thus, by simply doubling the polar group of the
512 amphiphile (i.e. one or two OH groups), SUPRAS with very different nanostructures
513 (sponges from 1,2-octanediol and inverted hexagonal aggregates from 1-octanol) and
514 composition (mainly arising from their distinct water content and consequently the extent
515 of their hydrophilic region) can be obtained, independently of the medium used for
516 coacervation. These differences were found to greatly impact their capability for the
517 extraction of polyphenols from raspberries. Thus, the sponge-like structure of SUPRAS
518 of 1,2-octanediol, that contains abundant aqueous interconnected channels (35.5-39%
519 w/w), solubilised more efficiently a wider polarity range of phenolic compounds.
520 SUPRAS of 1,2-octanediol and 1,3-propanediol provided a total polyphenolic content of
521 9.57 ± 0.19 mg GAE/g FW sample, a value that was around three times higher than that
522 obtained with pure ethanol. 1-Octanol-based SUPRAS extracted polyphenols less
523 efficiently being the best results obtained with those prepared in THF (4.16 ± 0.18 mg
524 GAE/g FW sample). The LC-MS/MS profile of SUPRAS extracts revealed the presence
525 of quercetin, naringenin, kaempferol, coumaric acid and catechin and their glycosides
526 together with chlorogenic acid and procyanidin.

527 It is known that the potential of SUPRAS for the extraction of compounds in a wide
528 polarity range is mainly due to the presence of polar and nonpolar microenvironments in
529 their nanostructures, being one of their most outstanding features. This study shows that
530 the broadening of the polar region greatly improves the extraction capability of polar
531 compounds, a factor here firstly investigated. These results highlight the need for more
532 fundamental studies related to the application of SUPRAS in the extraction of bioactive
533 compounds from biomass so that knowledge-based processes can be implemented to take
534 advantage of the opportunities arising from their tailoring.

535 **Declaration of competing interest**

536 The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal
537 relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

538

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